

Temporal and Spatial Dynamics of Heatwave-Wildfire Relationships over Africa

Frank Sonntag¹, Sathvi Kwatra²

Appendix

A1. Data: sources and pre-processing

ERA5 data was downloaded from ECMWF's CDS (Climate Data Store) at 0.25-degree resolution from <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/datasets/reanalysis-era5-land>. The daily 2-meter maximum temperature is calculated by selecting the highest value for each 24-hour day in the dataset. Heatwaves are defined as occurrences of at least three consecutive days where the daily 2-meter maximum temperature is above the 90th percentile of the seasonal mean for that day of the year. The seasonal mean for each day is calculated as a centered 11-day rolling average using the years 1981 to 2020 inclusive.

Vapor Pressure Deficit (VPD) is calculated using hourly temperature and dew point data, as described by Dee et al. (2011), and then averaged for each day.

To identify drought conditions, we use the Global SPEI database downloaded from <https://spei.csic.es/database.html> (Beguería et al., 2014). The monthly 0.5-degree SPEI data is regridded to match the 0.25-degree ERA5 grid using linear interpolation.

Fire counts are obtained from NASA's active fire product FIRMS (NASA FIRMS, 2020) and downloaded from <https://firms.modaps.eosdis.nasa.gov/download/>. The event-based spot data is converted into a daily gridded dataset by adding up fire events in each grid cell. We only use fire events that are flagged at at least the 75% confidence level.

We also look at burned area data as an alternative fire metric and used MODIS FireCCI 5.1 (Lizundia-Loiola et al., 2020) downloaded from CEDA (https://dap.ceda.ac.uk/neodc/esacci/fire/data/burned_area/MODIS/grid/v5.1/) as a grid data product. We found the initially used ECMWF FireCCI dataset to have a bug, which was reported to ECMWF.

The 300-meter resolution land cover data is upscaled to the 0.25-degree grid by using the most common land cover type to set the lower-resolution grid cell value.

A2. Data: selection of study period and areas based on available satellite data

The FIRMS active fire and FireCCI burned area products are available for the period 2001 - 2020 and are based on the MODIS on board the Terra and Aqua satellite platforms (Lizundia-Loiola et al., 2020).

The Aqua platform however came online only in July 2002 leading to an undercount of fire activity (Fig. A1). To ensure a consistent data set, we therefore limit our period of interest to the years 2003 to 2020 inclusive. Our two study regions are chosen to include the main areas with fire activity; one north and one south of the equator (Fig. A2).

Figure A1: Fires detected per month for each satellite platform

Figure A2: Total number of fires per grid cell

A3. Information Flow

To further interrogate the relationship between heat waves and wildfires, we calculate the information flow from heat wave frequency to number of detected fires. Information flow based on the concept of Shannon entropy has been shown to be a measure for the causal (linear and non-linear) relationship between variables (Liang, 2014).

The information flow method, proposed by Liang (2014), provides an approach for quantifying causal interactions in dynamical systems by measuring the rate of information transfer between variables. This framework is applicable to both the stochastic and deterministic systems without requiring linearity assumptions. The method calculates directional information flow (e.g., from variable X2 to X1, denoted $T_{2 \rightarrow 1}$) which is inherently asymmetric ($T_{2 \rightarrow 1} \neq T_{1 \rightarrow 2}$), thereby helps distinguishing causality from spurious associations.

In our study, we computed the information flow from heatwave frequency to fire counts using monthly aggregated time series restricted to fire seasons data for each grid cell (Fig. A2) and also for regionally averaged time series (not shown). We used the existing python code provided by Dr. Daniel Hagan to calculate the information flow, ignoring values with less than 90% significance (Fig. A2)

Overall we do not see a strong causal relationship between heat wave frequency and fire count.

Figure A2: Information flow from heatwave frequency to fire count

A4. Correlations

While we see Spearman correlation coefficients above 0.4 for most grid cells in the study region and even above 0.8 for some areas (Fig. A3) those values are not statistically significant, showing p-values well below 0.2 (Fig. A4). These findings suggest that other

factors, potentially land management practices, fire suppression efforts, or shifts in vegetation types, may be playing a more dominant role in the declining fire activity.

Figure A3: Spearman correlation between monthly heatwave frequency and monthly number of fires for months with SPEI < -1

Figure A4: Statistical significance of Spearman correlation between monthly heatwave frequency and monthly number of fires.